

Value Added Tax and Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Time Series Analysis (1986-2023)

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Abstract

Original Research Article

Taxation plays a central role in modern economic development, primarily due to its position as the most substantial source of government revenue. Among the various forms of taxation, indirect taxes such as the Value Added Tax (VAT) stand out as key instruments for revenue generation. The Finance Act of 2020 brought a significant policy shift in Nigeria by raising the VAT rate from 5% to 7.5%, effective from February 1, 2020. This study, therefore, investigates the impact of VAT and inflation on Nigeria's economic growth over the period 1986 to 2023. Secondary time series data were collected from the statistical bulletins of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach was employed to analyse the dataset. Findings of the study shows that VAT has a positive and statistically significant effect on GDP in both the short and long run, whereas inflation (INF) has a significant negative impact on economic growth across the same periods. Additionally, the error correction mechanism (ECM) suggests that any short-run disequilibrium in the model is gradually corrected in the long run, confirming the existence of a stable long-term relationship. In light of these findings, it is recommended that policymakers adopt a VAT strategy that enhances revenue generation while limiting inflationary pressures on consumer prices.

Keywords: Value Added Tax, Inflation, Economic Growth, ARDL.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The provision of essential public services—such as education, security, electricity, water, and healthcare—relies significantly on the government's ability to generate revenue, primarily through taxation (Ogundele, 1996). This underscores the importance of financial resources in promoting economic development and growth. Governments strive to meet key macroeconomic goals like full employment, stable prices, and sustained economic expansion through various policy tools, including indirect taxes. One major example of such a tax is the Value Added Tax (VAT), which is a consumption-based tax imposed at different stages of the production and distribution process but ultimately paid by the final consumer (Odunsi, 2022; Oserogho & Associates, 2008). According to Tabansi (2001), VAT applies to both locally produced and imported goods and services. Soyode and Kajola (2006) note that VAT is not only borne by end users but also has

the advantage of being easy to manage and hard to avoid. Kareem, Arije, and Avovome (2020) further explain that VAT is calculated based on the estimated increase in market value added at each phase of production or distribution, with each addition incorporated into the final price paid by consumers. Unlike consumers, businesses can reclaim the VAT they pay on their inputs, as these are typically used to create other goods or services that will either be sold further along the supply chain or directly to end users. VAT is applied consistently at each stage of the value chain based on the value added.

Value Added Tax (VAT) has emerged as a significant revenue generator in Sub-Saharan Africa and across many developing nations. It has consistently contributed a large share of total government tax income, and its successful implementation in numerous countries played a key role in Nigeria's decision to adopt it in 1993 (Ajakaiye, 2000). According to Ebrill et al. (2002), VAT is an efficient way to raise funds, linking its use to a higher proportion of

government tax revenue and overall improved revenue performance. The funds generated through VAT have the potential to drive economic growth. Economic growth refers to a long-term rise in a country's production capacity, typically measured by year-to-year changes in gross national product, per capita output, or net national product, all of which reflect an outward shift in the production possibility frontier (Salami, Apelogun, Omidia & Ojoye, 2015). As explained by Business Standard (2022b), it involves the annual increase in a nation's output and income resulting from economic activities by its citizens, both domestically and internationally. This measure accounts for the net increase in production across sectors after adjusting for inflation. The Central Bank of Nigeria (2010) defines economic growth as the expansion in the volume of goods and services produced over time, typically measured as the percentage increase in real gross domestic product (GDP), with inflation effects excluded to reflect true growth.

The legal foundation for the introduction of Value Added Tax (VAT) in Nigeria is Decree 102 of 1993, though the tax system officially came into effect in 1994. Initially, VAT was set at a rate of 5% on all eligible goods and services, whether produced locally or exported (Olatunji, 2009). This rate was later increased to 7.5% in 2020 following the enactment of the Finance Act. Since its inception, VAT has proven to be a successful source of government revenue in Nigeria. Data from the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) shows a significant increase in VAT collections—from N8.20 billion in 1994 to N163.30 billion by 2004, marking a ten-year period of growth. This figure continued to rise, reaching N616.90 billion in 2014 and peaking at N1.7 trillion in 2018. However, in 2019, revenue dropped slightly to N1.17 trillion—a decrease of N53 billion from the previous year. Despite challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic, VAT revenue continued to climb, hitting N1.53 trillion in 2020, N2.1 trillion in 2021, N2.51 trillion in 2022, and reaching an impressive N3.6 trillion in 2023 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2024). VAT is collected by registered businesses and organizations on behalf of the government, under the supervision of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (Olatunji, 2009).

Value Added Tax (VAT) is widely recognized for its relatively low susceptibility to tax evasion. Nevertheless, as Naiyeju (2010) observed, the implementation of VAT can contribute to upward pressure on prices, potentially resulting in inflation. Furthermore, the broad coverage of VAT often entails substantial administrative costs. The anticipated rise in the prices of goods and services associated with VAT may adversely impact societal welfare, thereby undermining the fundamental objectives of the tax system. However, Naiyeju (2010) further argued that the success of any tax measure is contingent upon its accurate interpretation, effective implementation, and sound management. In addition, the degree of public awareness and understanding significantly influences the extent to which the tax achieves its intended goals. In a related perspective, Rena (2011) emphasized the importance of a sustainable fiscal policy framework in fostering economic growth. He contended that such a framework should be grounded in the efficient delivery of

reliable public goods and services, long-term strategic investments, comprehensive tax reforms, and proactive measures to address social exclusion, all aimed at enhancing the overall quality of life for citizens.

It is in light of the above background that this study is carried out to empirically assess the relationship between value added tax and economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- i. What is the effect of value added tax on economic growth in Nigeria?
- ii. What is the effect of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Literature

2.1.1 Concept of Value Added Tax

The concept of Value Added Tax (VAT) has been defined from multiple perspectives, including its incidence, collection point, and tax base. Muhammed (1995) characterized VAT as a consumption tax aimed primarily at taxing the personal consumption of goods and services by individuals. Naiyeju (2014) described it as a tax imposed on the value added at each stage of the sale process. Ogundele (1996) provided a definition based on the 'addition method,' where the tax base comprises the total of wages and capital income, further clarifying it as the difference between a firm's sales and its input purchases. VAT is classified as an indirect tax, meaning it is collected from entities other than those who ultimately bear the tax burden. According to Bickley (1996), VAT is applied at every stage of production. Similarly, Oldman and Woods (1996) defined it as a multi-stage consumption tax calculated as the difference between a firm's total sales and the value of its input purchases. Ogundele (1996) also highlighted that VAT is imposed on the incremental value added to goods and services throughout the production and distribution chain, as well as during service delivery. Broadway (1979) viewed VAT in terms of its base, noting that it ultimately targets the final value of goods. Magner (1983) conceptualized VAT as a systematic approach to assigning tax liabilities based on the value added at each phase of the production and distribution process.

What stands out across these various definitions is that they collectively emphasize three fundamental features of Value Added Tax: it is a tax on consumption, its burden ultimately falls on the final consumer, and it is applied at multiple stages throughout the supply chain. Consequently, this study conceptualizes VAT as a form of Goods and Services Tax (GST), imposed on the incremental value generated at each point of transaction.

2.1.2 Concept of Economic Growth

Economic growth has long been a central objective of economic policy, with extensive scholarly attention devoted to understanding the mechanisms through which it can be realized (Fadare, 2010). Dewett (2005) defined economic growth as an increase in net national product over a specified period, characterizing it

as a quantitative enhancement of economic variables. He identified several key drivers of growth, including natural resource availability, capital accumulation, the capital-output ratio, technological advancements, and entrepreneurial activity. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (2010), economic growth refers to the expansion of goods and services produced within an economy over time and is typically measured by the percentage increase in real Gross Domestic Product (GDP), adjusted for inflation to reflect actual growth. Obadan and Okojie (2010) similarly described it as an annual rise in per capita output.

The International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2013) viewed economic growth as the real-term increase in the market value of goods and services produced within an economy, generally measured by the growth rate of real GDP, often expressed on a per capita basis. Matiti (2013) differentiated growth from development by defining the former as a quantitative expansion of an economic system without structural change, while describing development as a qualitative, transformative process. Morakinyo, David, and Alao (2018) conceptualized economic growth as an expansion in a nation's productive capacity or potential GDP. They argued that growth can be enhanced when public investment yields social returns exceeding private returns, highlighting the role of tax policy in accelerating growth. Additionally, growth theories that factor in public services suggest that optimal tax policy depends on the characteristics of these services. Economic growth theory thus aids in understanding disparities in growth rates among countries and guides government decisions on taxation and public expenditure.

Drawing from these perspectives, this study defines economic growth as a sustained, quantitative increase in the production of goods and services over a defined period, typically one year. Achieving such growth necessitates the implementation of effective fiscal policy, including the strategic use of government spending—both recurrent and capital—tax revenues, and public borrowing, all directed toward productive sectors of the economy to foster investment, employment, price stability, and overall output expansion.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 The Laffer Curve Theory

This study is grounded in the Laffer Curve theory, which serves as its theoretical framework. Introduced by Professor Arthur Laffer in 2004, the theory posits that there exists an optimal tax rate at which government revenue is maximized. Beyond this critical point, any further increase in tax rates may lead to a decline in revenue, as higher taxes can discourage economic activities such as work, investment, and income declaration. Essentially, the Laffer Curve illustrates the conceptual relationship between tax rates and the amount of revenue a government can generate, emphasizing that both excessively low and excessively high tax rates can lead to suboptimal revenue outcomes. The graphical representation—known as the Laffer Curve—depicts this relationship, highlighting the point at which tax policy can most effectively enhance government income. The Laffer curve is shown in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Laffer curve

The Laffer Curve theory explores the relationship between tax rates and the total revenue generated, particularly emphasizing the outcomes at the extremes of 0% and 100% taxation. It posits that both a zero and a full (100%) tax rate would yield no revenue: a 0% rate generates nothing by definition, while a 100% rate eliminates any motivation for individuals to earn taxable income, resulting in no taxable base. Consequently, the theory suggests that there must be at least one intermediate tax rate that maximizes revenue collection. Laffer traces the origins of this concept to earlier thinkers such as Ibn

Khaldun and John Maynard Keynes. A key implication of the theory is that increasing the Value Added Tax (VAT) rate beyond a certain threshold could be counterproductive, leading to diminishing returns in revenue due to reduced economic activity (Laffer, as cited in Afuberoh & Okoye, 2014). This theoretical framework is pertinent to the present study as it provides insight into identifying an optimal VAT rate that can enhance government revenue generation without triggering inflationary pressures or destabilizing the economy.

2.3 Empirical Review

Kareem, Arije, and Avovome (2020) conducted an empirical investigation into the relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) and economic growth in Nigeria using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model. Their analysis covered the period from 1994 to 2017 and focused on the interaction between VAT and Real Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The findings revealed a significant and positive impact of VAT on Nigeria's economic growth in both the short and long term. Additionally, the causality test indicated a directional relationship between VAT and economic growth during the study period. However, a key limitation of their research is the exclusion of inflation from the model, thereby overlooking the potential influence of VAT on general price levels—a gap this current study aims to address.

Similarly, Onoja and Ibrahim (2020) analyzed the link between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria between 2003 and 2017 through regression analysis. Their results showed a significant relationship between VAT and GDP, aligning with the findings of Harvest and Ataisi (2022), who examined the VAT-GDP relationship from 2000 to 2020 and reported similar outcomes. Chigbu and Ali (2014) utilized the Engle and Granger Co-integration method to assess the impact of VAT on Nigeria's economic growth from 1994 to 2012. While their results indicated a positive relationship between VAT and GDP, the analysis did not support the existence of either short-run or long-run co-integration. As with the earlier studies, both Onoja and Ibrahim and Chigbu and Ali did not incorporate inflation into their models, which limits the robustness of their findings. This present study seeks to enhance previous research by accounting for inflation as a moderating variable.

Gelardi (2014) employed graphical and statistical techniques to analyze the impact of Value Added Tax (VAT) on inflation in the United Kingdom and Canada. The study found that the introduction of VAT in the United Kingdom did not significantly affect the rate of change in the Consumer Price Index (CPI). However, the introduction of the General Sales Tax (GST) in Canada led to a notable increase in CPI. The research also concluded that significant changes in tax rates influenced inflation, while minor rate adjustments had no discernible effect. Although Gelardi's study provides valuable insights, it was conducted outside Nigeria, making its findings less applicable to the Nigerian context. Therefore, this current study focuses specifically on Nigeria, with its results and recommendations intended for local application.

Bakare (2013) explored the influence of VAT on Nigeria's output growth using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression approach. The study found a statistically significant and positive relationship between VAT and output growth. It also suggested that historical VAT values could be utilized to forecast future output trends. However, this conclusion has been critiqued for being potentially misleading, as future economic growth can be influenced by numerous other factors such as technological advancement, labor and input costs, and fiscal or monetary policy measures—variables that were not controlled for in Bakare's model.

Atan (2013) explored the efforts by successive Nigerian governments to use taxation as a tool to influence macroeconomic variables, particularly inflation and unemployment. Using secondary data from 1970 to 2008, the study employed both descriptive and inferential statistical methods, with Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression for estimation. The findings indicated that taxes had a negative but statistically insignificant effect on inflation, which aligned with theoretical expectations. Similarly, the study found an insignificant negative impact of tax policy on unemployment. Atan's study differs from the current research in that it did not focus on a specific tax policy and its direct effects on inflation and unemployment. Consequently, his findings may not provide a precise understanding of how specific tax policies impact these economic variables.

Olatunji (2013) examined the relationship between VAT and inflation in Nigeria from 1990 to 2003. His results showed that inflation was lower in 1994, the year VAT was introduced, compared to any year since 1990, suggesting that VAT did not contribute to inflation. In contrast, Ikpeh and Nteegah (2013) used partial equilibrium analysis to investigate the economic impact of VAT on aggregate prices from 1994 to 2010. Their results indicated that VAT exerted upward pressure on price levels, likely due to the tax burden on intermediate goods. Olatunji's study, while insightful, is limited by its narrow time frame, which may not reflect the broader economic realities of Nigeria at the time. Ikpeh and Nteegah's methodology differs from that of the current study, offering a unique approach to analyzing VAT's economic impact.

Unegbu and Ireferin (2010) adopted both primary and secondary data sources and employed regression analysis, discriminant analysis, and ANOVA to test their hypotheses. Their results showed that VAT allocations accounted for 91.2% of the variation in the expenditure pattern of Adamawa State between 2001 and 2009. While they concluded that VAT significantly influenced public spending, respondents in the state perceived that VAT had a limited impact on both economic and human development. Nonetheless, the reliability of their results is questionable due to their reliance on primary data, which introduces potential biases and limits the generalizability of their conclusions.

Kleiman (1993) analyzed the role of taxation in explaining national price levels and their deviation from Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) by examining 51 countries. The study concluded that indirect taxes, particularly those imposed by central governments, contributed to higher general price levels, especially for tradables. However, this study, conducted prior to the introduction of VAT in Nigeria, is less relevant to the current analysis of VAT's effects on the Nigerian economy.

The reviewed literature reveals an ongoing and unresolved debate regarding the effects of VAT on inflation and economic growth. Given the recent changes in Nigerian tax policies, particularly the VAT increase to 7.5% following the 2020 financial bill, there is a pressing need for accurate and up-to-date information. This study seeks to address this gap, especially in light of the rising government expenditure amid declining tax revenue and the increasing costs of goods and services.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Method and Sources of Data

The research design for this study adopts a quantitative approach, which involves the collection and analysis of data in numerical form. The decision to use a quantitative method stems from the availability of established secondary data for the study's variables. Initially, an Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test is conducted to assess the time-series properties of the variables in the model. Following this, a co-integration test is performed to examine whether the variables move together over time. To estimate both the short-run and long-run effects, an ARDL model is employed. Data covering the period from 1986 to 2023 was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) statistical reports, and the analysis was conducted using E-Views 12 econometric software.

3.2 Model Specification

To examine the effect of value added tax on economic growth in Nigeria, this study adopts the model

used by Olatunji (2013) and Ikpeh and Nteegah (2013). GDP which measures economic growth is used as the dependent variable, while VAT and INF is used as the independent variables.

The model for this study can be expressed mathematically as follows:

$$GDP = f(VAT, INFR_t) \quad (1)$$

Thus, the econometric equation above can be specified in dynamic logarithmic form as:

$$GDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log VAT_t + \beta_2 \log INFR_t + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

Where:

GDP = Gross Domestic Product

VAT = Value Added Tax

INF = Inflation

Log = Natural logarithm

β_0 = intercept or constant

β_1 and β_2 = Coefficients of the explanatory variables, VAT and INF

t = The time under study (2000-2023)

μ = The error term

A priori expectation: $\beta_1 > 0$; that is, β_1 is expected to be positive, and $\beta_2 < 0$; that is, β_2 is expected to be negative.

4. PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	VAT	INF
Mean	341.7890	772.6102	16.31000
Maximum	574.1800	2721.630	72.80000
Minimum	69.17000	12.30000	5.400000
Skewness	-0.681646	0.853726	2.880299
Kurtosis	2.538611	2.556191	10.90729
Jarque-Bera	2.589309	3.890453	119.6371
Probability	0.273992	0.142955	0.000000
Observations	30	30	30

Source: Computation from study data (2025) using eviews 12

The descriptive statistics offered valuable insights into the time-series data over the study period, highlighting significant variance and deviations from normal distribution. The data for all variables showed large differences between the minimum and maximum values in comparison to the means, indicating a wide spread. The skewness values suggest asymmetry, with negative skewness observed for GDP and positive skewness for VAT and inflation (INF). The kurtosis results indicate

leptokurtic distributions, characterized by fat tails, for all variables. The Jarque-Bera test rejects normality for inflation, although the results for the other variables are inconclusive. With 30 observations per variable, the dataset provides a sufficient sample size. The key takeaways include high variability, asymmetry, heavy tails, and non-normal distributions, which provide a foundation for further analysis.

4.2 Unit Root Test

Table 4.2: Summary of Augmented Dicky-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF Statistics	5% Critical Value	P. Value	Order of Integration	Remark
GDP	-5.166467	-3.540328	0.0009	I(1)	Stationary
VAT	-3.627773	-3.612199	0.0485	I(1)	Stationary
INF	-4.292670	-3.540328	0.0087	I(0)	Stationary

Source: Computation from study data (2025) using eviews 12

From table 4.2, the variables were tested for stationarity, and the results indicated that GDP and VAT became stationary at the first difference, I(1), while inflation (INF) was stationary at the level, I(0). This combination of I(0)

and I(1) variables is suitable for applying the ARDL bounds testing approach, which can accommodate variables with different integration orders.

4.3 ARDL Estimation

4.3.1 ARDL Bounds Test

Table 4.3: ARDL Bounds Test Result

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	12.47728	10%	4.19	5.06
K	2	5%	4.87	5.85
		2.5%	5.79	6.59
		1%	6.34	7.52

Source: Computation from study data (2025) using eviews 12

The computed F-statistic (12.47728) is higher than the upper bound critical value at 5% significance level, confirming the existence of cointegration among the

variables. This points to a stable long-run relationship between the variables.

4.3.2 ARDL Short-Run Estimation

Table 4.4: ARDL Short-run Estimation Result
Dependent Variable: D(GDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1314.751	199.4624	-6.591474	0.0001
LOG(VAT)(-1))	0.585459	0.169981	3.444265	0.0063
LOG(INF)(-1))	-12.73356	3.959888	-3.215637	0.0092
ECM(-1)	-0.441109	0.065816	-6.702104	0.0001
R-squared	0.842087			
Adjusted R-squared	0.671015			
F-statistic	4.922405			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.004630			

Source: Computation from study data (2025) using eviews 12

The results indicate a positive and significant relationship between GDP and VAT at the 5% significance level, while there is a negative and significant relationship between GDP and inflation (INF), also at the 5% level, which aligns with prior expectations. The negative constant (C)

suggests that, holding VAT and INF constant, GDP would decrease. The error correction term (ECM), which serves to restore equilibrium and confirm the existence of a long-term equilibrium relationship between the variables, is both negative and significant at the 5% level, as

anticipated. The ECM coefficient of -0.441109 indicates that the system returns to equilibrium at a rate of 44% in response to long-term shocks. This suggests a gradual adjustment process, reflected in the lower coefficient value. This supports the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables. The

goodness of fit (R-squared) indicates that 84% of the variation in the dependent variable (GDP) is explained by the independent variables (VAT and INF). The F-statistic reveals that the overall model remains significant after adjustment, as shown by the probability value of 0.004630.

4.3.3 ARDL Long-Run Estimation

Table 4.5: ARDL Long-run Coefficient Estimates
Dependent Variable: D(GDP)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-1314.751	319.8985	-4.109902	0.0021
VAT	0.585459	0.198793	2.945066	0.0147
INF	-12.73356	4.750402	-2.680523	0.0231

Source: Computation from study data (2025) using eviews 12

The long-run estimates reveal important insights into the relationships between the variables and long-term economic growth. The VAT coefficient (0.585459) shows a positive and significant impact on GDP, suggesting that VAT revenue contributes to economic growth in the long

run. In contrast, the INF coefficient (-12.73356) indicates a negative and significant effect on GDP, implying that a higher inflation rate will hinder economic growth over the long term.

4.4 ARDL Post-Estimation Tests

4.4.1 Serial Correlation Test Result

Table 4.6: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test Result

F-statistic	0.239369	Prob. F(2,8)	0.7926
Obs*R-squared	1.468047	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.4800

Source: Computation from study data (2025) using eviews 12

Table 4.6 shows the result of the test for serial correlation in the model. The p-value for both F-statistics (0.7926) and observed R-squared (0.4800) are above 5% level of

significance. This means that the model does not suffer from both first and second order serial correlation.

4.4.2 Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH

Table 4.7: Heteroskedasticity Test Result

F-statistic	0.687505	Prob. F(2,21)	0.5138
Obs*R-squared	1.474870	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.4783

Source: Computation from study data (2025) using eviews 12

Table above shows the result of the test for heteroskedasticity in the model. The p-value for both F-statistics (0.5138) and observed R-squared (0.4783) are

above 5% level of significance. This means that the model does not suffer from heteroskedasticity.

4.4.3 CUSUM Stability Test

Figure 2: CUSUM

As observed from figure 2 and 3, both the CUSUM and CUSUM-SQ results indicate parameter stability as the cumulative sum is in the area between the two critical lines. The parameters are adjudged to be stable within that year indicated by the graph. This implies that the coefficients in the model are constant and the relationships estimated are reliable.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

The ARDL regression estimates indicate that the intercept of the regression line is -1314.751, suggesting a decline in economic growth (GDP) if VAT and inflation rate (INF) are held constant. This demonstrates that both VAT and INF are key factors influencing economic growth during the study period. In both the short-run and long-run, VAT has a positive and significant effect on GDP, aligning with a priori expectations. This indicates that an increase in VAT revenue leads to a notable rise in GDP. These findings align with the study of Kareem, Arije, and Avovome (2020), who found a positive and significant impact of VAT on Nigeria's economic growth in both the short- and long-run. Conversely, INF is found to negatively and significantly affect GDP in both the short- and long-run, which is consistent with a prior expectation. This suggests that higher inflation leads to a substantial reduction in GDP. This contrasts with Olatunji's (2013) study, who found that inflation was lower in 1994 when VAT was introduced, indicating that VAT did not cause inflation. Overall, the goodness of fit (R-squared) confirms that VAT and INF significantly influence GDP, as reflected by their coefficients and associated probability values.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, this study confirms the laffer curve theory which highlighted that increasing VAT rate beyond a certain point will become counterproductive for raising further tax revenue because of diminishing returns and may exert pressure on prices of goods and services. In the short-run and over the long-run, VAT and INF have significant influence on the economic growth in Nigeria over the period under study. Based on the findings of the

Figure 3: CUSUM-SQ

study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Pursue a favourable and sustainable VAT rate that will lead to increase in government revenue while minimising pressure on the prices of goods and services
- ii. Carefully pursue inflation rate that improves aggregate demand and output of goods and services.

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